

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF MUSICAL- THEORETICAL SCIENCES IN IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article talks about the importance of improving the professional-pedagogical skills of future music teachers and professional competence, which is considered one of its branches. Today, the effectiveness of music teachers' activities, preparation for starting pedagogical activities, first of all, the importance of pedagogical skills, the possession of the types of competences necessary in each pedagogical process, is highlighted in the activity. The importance of music-theoretical sciences in increasing creativity and professional competence was touched upon.

Key words: musical culture, moral education, aesthetics, activity, pedagogy, pedagogical skill, competence, component, expert.

Introduction:

In the development of the field of education, it is important to train pedagogical staff in a way that is knowledgeable and meets the requirements of the times. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "... we rely on our mature, ambitious, enterprising young people who have thoroughly mastered modern knowledge and skills in order to further increase the scope and effectiveness of our reforms, ... young people who think independently and logically based on modern knowledge and experiences, national and universal values, We will raise people with good qualities"¹, New Uzbekistan defined the issue of personnel training as an urgent task in choosing its path in economic and social development.

Higher education institutions, which are an important stage of continuous education, are of particular importance in the implementation of this task. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" focuses on the development of higher education institutions and the training of pedagogical personnel. "Higher education ensures the preparation of highly qualified personnel in undergraduate and master's fields of study...A bachelor's degree provides in-depth knowledge, skills and abilities in one of the fields of higher education, winter duration is at least three years of basic higher education."².

The knowledge and potential of future teachers who are preparing for pedagogical activities in higher education institutions is one of the most necessary factors that determine the quality of general secondary education. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 5, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country" Resolution No. PD-3775, dated October 8, 2019, Decree No. PF-5847, dated April 29, 2019, "On approval of the concept of development of the system of public

¹ O'zbekiston Respublikasining Ta'lim to'g'risidagi Qonuni,. O'RQ-637-son 23.09.2020-yil.

² Karimov I.A. "Yuksak ma'naviyat-yengilmas kuch". Ma'naviyat nashriyoti, Toshkent., 2008-yil.

education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", "Development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 until PF-60 Decree No. PF-60 on to provide future pedagogues who can use advanced pedagogical and information technologies in their activities and implement the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications creates the need to educate as a capable, creative person.

Citizens of the country strive for perfection in all aspects and become the main factor of the state's development. Education of students and young people who have their own independent opinion, intellectually mature, sound-thinking, and highly professional, along with the acquisition of knowledge, remains one of the urgent issues in this direction. The first President Islam Karimov stated that *"...the foundation of our future is created in the fields of knowledge, in other words, the future of our nation depends on the education and upbringing of our children today"*³. Therefore, the ultimate goal of music education is: *"to bring up adults who can perceive music, mature, mature, cultured, not only aware of their own national traditions, but also aware of the culture of other nations and respect this tradition and culture."*⁴

Taking into account that the pedagogue plays the main role in the formation of the above aspects in children, it is not difficult to understand that the training of future music teachers determines the quality indicator of music culture. The professional formation of a teacher begins with the process of receiving professional education in higher education. Today, higher education as a leading institution of learning is of special importance in the development of society in the preparation of competitively qualified personnel. Currently, in our country, in higher pedagogical educational institutions, music education majors are taught in state and non-state pre-school educational organizations, general secondary schools, secondary specialized, vocational educational institutions, formation of children as pedagogical personnel for music and art schools. To improve their pedagogical and professional skills, professional competence and creativity while preparing them to work in the mass media, state management bodies, state and non-state institutions, and to improve the quality of modern pedagogues of tomorrow is one of the factors that determine the indicator.

It is noted that it is necessary to perform various types of activities and acquire skills during the training process of bachelors of higher education, in particular, the types of professional activities of bachelors during the 3-year study in music education are as follows:

- *pedagogical;*
- *scientific research;*
- *spiritual and educational;*
- *organizational management;*
- *production.*⁵

A bachelor's degree graduate should be able to perform several tasks in the pedagogical activity type of professional activities. It can be understood that the types of pedagogical activities, in turn, require the future music teacher to have professional competence and creativity and to improve them until the graduation process. In the course of training future

³ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi. President.uz sayti <https://president.uz/oz/lists/view/4057>. 2020-yil 29-dekabr.

⁴ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligi. 5111100 – *Musiqa ta'limi* bakalavriat ta'lim yo'nalishining malaka talablari. O'z.R. O.O'.M.T.V. Buyruq № , Toshkent 2020-yil.

⁵ "Musiqa nazariyasi". Fan dasturi. Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti. Toshkent 2020-yil.

music teachers at the undergraduate level, the subject "*Professional competence and creativity of a music teacher*" should be included in the curriculum. The purpose of teaching science is to describe science in the process of mastering theoretical and practical activities, on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies, to acquire knowledge, skills and qualifications related to the requirements for a professional competence approach to musical education and a creative approach to work. The task of science is the content of the education of innovative technologies of music education, pedagogical impact on the creativity of teachers and students, basic information about creative game and interactive technologies, innovative technologies and information technologies developing in music education. "*Preparation for independent study of best practices in the field of music education and upbringing*"⁶.

The extent to which subjects are mastered at the undergraduate level is important in developing the professional competence and creativity of future music teachers. If we look at the section of sciences, music-theoretical sciences are the main subjects of music education that determine the level of musical literacy. Artistic (*musical*) thinking competence, which should be developed in it, can be achieved through science - only when the teacher is able to think artistically and figuratively in his field, he can better introduce his students to the world of music. Music theory is a part of musicology that covers a complex of disciplines dealing with theoretical aspects. Music theory is a generalizing concept of elementary theory of music, harmony, polyphony, musical form, solfeggio, instrumentation, rhythmic sciences.

In the musical education direction of the pedagogic directions of higher educational institutions, the subject "*Music theory*" is the subject, "the purpose of teaching the subject is to educate students' conscious thinking in relation to musical expressiveness and to form the ability to perceive it, to develop the musical outlook of students, formation and development of perception, correct orientation and enrichment of musical-aesthetic taste, development of creative abilities; is to prepare students for practical work as music teachers. The task of the subject is to provide students with in-depth knowledge in understanding the main means of musical expression and to teach musical and technical skills:

- to get acquainted with the important issues and main problems of the composer's work, and to give a clear understanding of the music system and the harmony that occupies an important place in it;
- to acquaint students with the basic laws of the structure of the form of a musical work, important musical elements, principles of musical development, the function of parts in the form, and to form the skills of analyzing various musical forms;
- to form students' musical thinking, musical hearing, ability to feel pure intonation, and their musical memory, to educate them to have a sense of mood, rhythm, tempo, and style, and to teach them to apply the acquired knowledge in practice⁷.

A future music teacher, who will master the subjects for 3 years, will develop several competencies in musical-theoretical subjects by means of topics, theoretical and practical

⁶ "Musiqqa o'qituvchisining kasbiy kompetentligi va kreativligi". Fan dasturi. Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti. Toshkent 2020-yil.

⁷ Drapeau Sparking student creativity (practical ways to promote innovative thinking and problem solving). – Alexandria – Virginia, USA: ASCD, 2014.

assignments. Including: as a result of teaching the subject "*Theory of musical elements*", the student:

- characteristics of musical sound, musical system, notation system, rhythm, meter, scale, tempo, conducting rules, interval, key, tonality, tonalities circle of fifths, chord, folk keys, alteration, chromaticism, chromatic gamma, transposition, tonalities they will have ideas and knowledge about step, deviation, modulation, melody, musical signs, signs of performance style;

- write sounds correctly on the note path, transpose, create a sound line of major and minor tonalities, create intervals in different sounds and tonalities, solve them, make chords from sounds, solve them, determine their tonality and create chords in tonalities, folk music sound lines they will acquire the skills of composition, determination, written and practical composition of chromatic gammas;

- they will have the skills to determine intervals, chords, scales, determine the tempo and tonality of works, and analyze the character of images.

Future music teachers in the harmony course:

- imagination and knowledge about harmonic laws, harmonic analysis, chords and their properties in harmony;

- chord structure, writing chords in a four-tone structure, adding chords, the correct direction of voices, the joint movement of voices, harmonizing melody and bass, creating their rotations and solutions, using chords in harmonic cycles, chord sequence - they will have the skills to play sequences and sequences on the piano.

Students in the music analysis course:

- acquires theoretical knowledge about the form of a musical work, principles of development, important means of musical expression, homophonic and polyphonic types of structures, types of narration, structure of forms;

- acquires the skills to analyze the means of musical expression of any musical work, to determine the principles of the work's development, the types of narration, to analyze them while understanding the features of the work in different forms, to understand the character, means, and peculiarities of the themes of the musical work.

The solfeggio course is considered a laboratory part of music theory in which students:

- understand the practical importance of solfeggio, sing one- and two-part melodies in pure intonation, write musical dictation, identify musical elements by listening, create an accompaniment to a melody, have ideas and knowledge about laws and rules;

- solfedgio of examples of one- and two-voice folk, classical and modern works in a pure, meaningful, correct manner, according to the character, paying attention to dynamic signs, notating them while listening, periodicity sing sequences composed of passed chords in the form; sing tonally and modulating monophonic and homophonic-harmonic and polyphonic polyphonic samples with chromatic sounds; identify intervals, chords, chords by listening, be able to sing a given melody in transposition, one and two-voice melodic dictation, interval dictation should be able to write.

For practical training, separate topics are given from the theory of elements of music, harmony, and analysis of musical works, which are part of the subject. Practical training should be conducted by one professor-teacher for one academic group in an auditorium equipped with multimedia devices. It is desirable that the classes should be conducted using

active and interactive methods, appropriate pedagogical and information technologies should be used. "As long as the future music teacher acquires all musical-theoretical knowledge from the subject of "*Music theory*" and can apply it in a practical way, he can be considered to have sufficient knowledge, skills and qualifications in this subject". At this point, it can be understood that theoretical studies are important for the activity of musical literacy. During the student's pedagogical activity, the types of activities of classes, that is, in the primary classes that we have listed above:

1. *Singing as a choir.*
2. *Music literacy.*
3. *Listening to music.*
4. *Performing movements to the music.*
5. *Accompanying children on musical instruments.*

In middle classes, music lessons are conducted on the basis of three types of activities:

1. *Singing in chorus.*
2. *Music literacy.*
3. *Listening to music is important in the organization of professional competence and creativity.*

It is natural that increasing professional competence and creativity in a higher education institution through the science of the same name and other theoretical, practical, creative knowledge will create a foundation for his formation as a potential pedagogue in the future teaching profession. Taking into account that all types of lesson activities require musical-theoretical knowledge, it is effective to increase the professional competence and creativity of the future music teacher during the bachelor's period by means of musical-theoretical sciences, so that he can demonstrate his professional competence in each type of activity and have a creative approach to the processes. In general, in music culture classes in general education schools, based on the essence of the subject, by using the types of activities in a different way, achieving a whole complex serves to increase the effectiveness of the lesson and increase the interest of children in science.

Analyzing that each type of activity is closely related to musical-theoretical sciences, we can understand that special attention should be paid to the pedagogue's acquisition of thorough knowledge in these sciences from the bachelor's period. In the organization of lessons according to the types of activities, the professional competence and creativity of the teacher is the leading factor in enriching traditionalism on the basis of a modern approach, and it is more appropriate if the professional competence and creativity of future music teachers is increased by means of music-theoretical sciences. As the goal is to increase the professional competence and creativity of the future music teacher through musical-theoretical subjects, it is also necessary to master these subjects in such a way that they can provide knowledge that the teacher can rely on in organizing and conducting lessons in the pedagogical activities of the future. special attention should be paid.

Conclusion:

Taking into account that being a creative pedagogue is the guarantee of a positive effect in the organization of lesson activities, in the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies in children through the activity type, which aspects of the future music teacher's creative aspects should be learned from the lesson activities taking into account that it is more accessible, as a

way to achieve the intended result in increasing the professional competence and creativity of the student through the means of music-theoretical sciences, the relationship between the type of lesson activity-competency-creativity parameter-leading music-theoretical science Systematized. Taking these connections into account, it was concluded that it is important to improve the professional competence and creativity of future music teachers through music-theoretical sciences.

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